

FROM PAN-AFRICANISM TO REGIONAL INTEGRATION: THE LIMITS OF CONVENTIONAL APPROACHES

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Abstract

Pan-Africanism, which exists today as regional integration, is a strategic ideology in African history. While the establishment of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) marked the institutionalisation of pan-Africanism in the continent, its transition to African Union (AU) heralded the embrace of the neo-liberal ideology. The divergences that characterised colonial pan-Africanism and post-colonial African regional integration processes produced the compromises that impacted the delivery of its ideals and the apparent lacklustre approach to economic decolonization. Drawing on historical evidence, this paper demonstrates that the attainment of a self-reliant development in Africa is elusive due to the inability of Afrocrats to formulate a strategically relevant approach to guide the evolution of a viable regional economic integration framework as conventional approaches exhibited profound inherent limitations to the African condition and incapable of resolving its development dilemma.

Keywords: *Pan-Africanism, Regionalism, Integration, Conventional, Approach.*

Introduction

Historically, the term *pan-Africanism* was first used by the Trinidadian lawyer, Sylvester Williams, to organise a congress of Blacks in London in 1900 to discuss European colonialism and foreign domination, racial prejudice, the inhuman treatment of Blacks, and the international standing of Haiti, Ethiopia, and Liberia (the only independent Black states at the time). Decolonisation was introduced by W. E. B. DuBois and adopted by the congress (Amate 1986: 34). The desire for and ideology of Black unity expressed in Negro solidarities like the American Negro Academy (1897), the National Association for the Advancement of Coloured People (1901), the Niagra Movement (1906), the Negro Society for Historical Research, Younders, New York (1911), etc., accelerated the development of the pan-African thought and notion of the African Personality (Thompson 1969: xxii).

Between 1900 and 1919, pan-Africanism symbolised the growth of nationalism among African, Afro-American and Afro-West Indian intellectuals, and boosted at the Manchester Pan-African Congress of 1945 attended by African

students who later led their homelands in the political decolonisation struggles (Amate 1986: 36-7). However, by the late 1920s, the pan-Africanist movement had splintered between DuBois who wanted Africans' participation in the governance of their colonies, and Marcus Garvey who sought to establish a bridgehead in Africa to fight colonialism and unite the Blacks (Thompson 1969: 42-3). Pan-African efforts of the 1920s and 1930s included: DuBois's National Association for the Advancement of Coloured People (NAACP); Garvey's Universal Negro Improvement Association, and the African Communities League; Casely-Hayford's National Council of British West Africa (NCBWA); Ladipo Solanke's West African Students Union, (WASU) (Asante and Chanaiwa 1993; Amate 1986; Thompson 1969; Hoskyns 1967).

Pan-Africanism also embraced *Negritude* (Edward Blyden); the *African Personality* (Blaise Diagne); *Presence Africaine* and the newspaper, *L' Etudiant Noir* (Leopold Sedar Senghor and Aime Cesaire) (Thompson 1969: 34-9; Gruhn 1979: 18; Asante and Chanaiwe 1993: 724). However, "the Italian invasion of Ethiopia (in 1935) gave African racial consciousness a far more boost" (Coleman 1958:

209). The simultaneity of efforts toward nationalism and integration were exemplified in NCBWA and WASU's conceptualisation of a West African union of independent states as a prelude to continental unity (Amate 1986: 39; Thompson 1969; Hoskyns 1967). In October 1946, the French West African states formed the *Rassemblement Democratique Africain* (RDA) under Felix Houphouet Boigny (Amate 1986: 37-8). In 1957, pan-Africanism found an African home with the attainment of political independence by Ghana. In 1958, Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana hosted the Conference of Independent African States (CIAS) and the All African Peoples Conference (AAPC), and declared the Ghana-Guinea Union on 1 May 1959 as the "nucleus of a nation of West African states" and basis of a "Union of Independent States of Africa" where "member-states would surrender portions of their national sovereignty in the full interest of the African community" (Amate 1986: 40).

However, Liberia's William Taubman rejected Nkrumah's position and proposed the "Associated States of Africa" on 19 July 1959 to frustrate Nkrumah's ambition (Amate 1986: 40). This began the pan-Africanist schism between the radicals and conservatives with divergent approaches to African integration and unity, which blossomed in the Brazzaville (later Monrovia) versus Casablanca blocs that produced a compromise charter for the Organisation of African Unity (OAU). According to Asante and Chanaiwa (1993: 728), "the continental integration aspect of pan-Africanism lost its momentum throughout the second half of the 1960s. It was rather replaced by movements for the formation of regional and inter-state groupings".

Theoretical approaches help to "map the political landscape" and clarify the contours of historical developments (Hurrell 1995: 72). Regional integration involves the establishment of joint institutional mechanisms by states within a regional contiguous area for a shared sovereignty to create a new polity and evolve a larger unit with a central authority (Hurrell 1995: 42; Lavergne 1997: 2; Christiansen 2005: 580). The Cold War bipolar system (1945-1990) profoundly influenced the political and economic outcomes of pan-Africanist and regional integration efforts in Africa and

beyond. Therefore, in the post-Cold War period, Africa must engage the "new regionalisms in ... terms of purposes, participants and processes" (Shaw 1993: 88). The primary objective of this work is to do a critical review of the conventional theoretical approaches to regional integration to show their limited applicability to the African condition and identify an alternative approach for the continent.

Conceptualising Pan-Africanism-An Overview

African descendants' struggles to survive in the politically and culturally inhospitable environment of the post-slavery New World evoked the idea of unity of action. Pan-Africanism, a gift of the New World to the Old World, represents a political movement and cultural phenomenon that regards Africa and Africans in the diasporas as a unit in the effort to establish a global African presence and the regeneration of the dignity of the Black race in reaction to the heritage of slavery that manifested in racism, imperialism and colonialism (Agubuzu 2004: 193; Asante and Chainawa 1993: 724; Agbi 1989: 154; Liebenow 1987: 365-7). Similarly, regional integration is "the process whereby actors in several distinct national settings are persuaded to shift their loyalties, expectations, and political activities towards a new centre whose institutions possess or demand jurisdiction over the pre-existing national states" (Ernst Hass, cited in Hurrell 1995: 60). Pan-Africanism as regional integration embraces the whole spectrum of efforts and schemes by post-colonial African leaders and statesmen to achieve continental political and cultural unity, and economic decolonisation (Hoskyns 1967: 354-93; Mayall 1995: 169-98; Bonchuk 2012: 232-7).

Post-colonial pan-African efforts and schemes were facilitated by existent pre-colonial pre-colonial social and economic structures and processes that involved the movement of goods and peoples across Africa. The Sahara was a major channel of commercial exchanges and the bridge that connected West to North Africa, while Islam, as a uniting force, provided the socio-cultural and political dynamics of huge interactions. The existence of sprawling empires like the Benin, Ghana, Kanem-Bornu, Mali, Maghreb, Oyo, and Songhai also provided the bonds that united diverse

peoples and promoted extensive cultural and commercial exchanges and diplomatic relations across the Sahara. By the onset of colonialism, these pre-colonial factors had warranted some form of integration within four main groups of African states, namely: the Maghreb, French West and Equatorial Africa, British West Africa, and East and Central Africa (Hoskyns 1967: 354).

The concept of pan-Africanism as regional integration is predicated on the philosophy of cultural and political unity, collective survival and group welfare maximization through the harmonisation of economic policies at the regional and global levels (Bourenane 1997; Olarenwaju and Falola 1987: 53; Asante and Chanaiwa 1993: 725). In 1958, the AAPC called for the elimination of tariff and non-tariff barriers for intra-African trade and conclusion of multi-lateral payments agreements for the establishment of an African common market. The United Nations Economic Commission for Africa established in 1958 supported the vision (Asante and Chanaiwa 1993: 725). However, the high politics of African states between 1960 and 1964 affected the integrative side of pan-Africanism leading to the evolution of over 200 regional and sub-regional organizations with overlapping objectives and very disappointing practical results. The pan-Africanism of the 1960s was synonymous with the regionalisation of political decolonisation which obscured the search for economic efficiency (Fredland 1990: 4).

The African trajectory contrasted with the position that "the early stages of integration tend to concentrate on the elimination of trade barriers and the formation of a customs union" (Hurrell 1995: 43). Okigbo (1993: 28-9) categorised pan-Africanism into four phases: struggle against slavery, European colonialism, neo-colonialism, and the privatisation of African states by indigenous monocratic rulers. Pan-Africanism as regional integration was envisioned as a counterweight strategy to the pervasive effects of globalisation. However, the inability of African regional frameworks to achieve this objective has been attributed to "the economic and political heterogeneity" of the states, the adoption of "different development paths", the intractability of

political and ideological cleavages (Asante and Chanaiwa 1993: 732). The simultaneity of the processes of integration and disintegration in Africa is due to the incidence of nationalism (Hazlewood 1967; Bonchuk 2012: 234).

Regional and sub-regional schemes for pooling of resources and harmonisation of economic policies transcended traditional bilateral to multilateral diplomatic engagement (Cooper 1996: 235-36; Jazbec 2001: 34). Some African sub-regional bodies include: the East African Community (1947), the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) (1975); the Southern African Development Coordination Conference (SADCC) now the Southern African Development Community (SADC) (1980); the Arab Maghreb Union (1980); the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS), the Central African equivalent of ECOWAS (1981); the Southern African States Preferential Trading Area (PTA) (1984), just to mention but a few. African states realised that the capacity to overcome their economic woes rests on regional economic integration and co-operative efforts in the pan-Africanist movement (Adedeji 1993: 407-8).

Andrew Wyatt-Walter (1995: 74-121) identifies global developments that influenced contemporary international disposition towards regionalism as: the effects of the end of the Cold War on the global political economy; the shifting balance of world economic power; and the shift towards outward- or export-oriented economic policies in the developing countries. The attendant collapse of multilateralism, the rise of new exclusive trading blocs, the revival of interest in regionalism, and the rise of nationalism should refocus Africa's regional economic integration attempts. The emergence of the European Economic Community (EEC) and Africa's deteriorating subordinate position in the New International Division of Labour (NIDL) aggravated by the breakdown of the Bretton Woods Agreement and persistent stagflation that exposed the extreme vulnerability of its economies in the contemporary neo-liberal world economic order should necessitate the development of innovative regional collective action and solidarity.

The EEC-ACP Lome Convention of 1975 was a vertical Euro-African orientation and consolidation of neo-colonialism to warrant pan-Africanist efforts towards reducing its over-dependence on former colonial powers, improving the bargaining power of African states, and contributing to a New International Economic Order (NIEO). Hence, *Afrocrats* experimented with the Monrovia Strategy for Economic Development in Africa (1979) as well as the Lagos Plan of Action and the Final Act of Lagos (1980) based on collective self-reliance (Asante 1991; Asante and Chanaiwa 1993: 735-40). However, the kind of solidarity expected of African states by structuralist theorists who, like the *dependencia*, advocated major structural reforms in the international system in the struggle against the exploitative relationship between the global South and the industrialised North did not materialise. Even the modest achievement of the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) in the early 1970s for a NIEO could not produce the much needed unity. Rather African power politics of the 1980s made the OAU "experienced serious difficulties in achieving a consensus among ... members across a wide range of issues" (Fawcett 1995: 16).

If the high politics of the Cold War dampened the prospects of pan-Africanism, its end and the decentralisation of the international system did boost Africa's new regionalism as a way of overcoming greater vulnerability in the post-Cold War neo-liberal order characterised by economic liberalisation and the concentration of global economic activities around four dominant poles: European Union, North America, Asia, and the Pacific Rim (Fawcett 1995: 22-6). Also, African states' apparent loss of the opportunity of being courted as bargaining chips by the United States of America and the Soviet Union for their favours through aid or trade that forced them to compete with the new states of Eastern Europe for loans, markets, humanitarian assistance enhanced the promotion of regional economic integration as the only rational choice.

The post-Cold War political liberalisation or "democratisation" produced a favourable environment for interdependence at the regional and

global levels. Democracy has never been a necessary condition for regionalism, but democratic institutions enhanced the making of desirable compromises in the construction of regional frameworks. Africa states' inability to build democratic institutions blocked the making of compromises required for successful regional blocs as demonstrated in the Americas, Asia and the Middle East currently (Fawcett 1995: 29). The evolution of strong democratic institutions capable of producing political stability and/or representative institutions in Africa would guarantee the foundations of a successful regional integration. However, the end of the Cold War did not end great power rivalries, but initiated "a new scramble for Africa" (Southall and Melber 2009). The new scramble deepened Africa's external linkages and vulnerability, encouraged intra-regional conflicts beyond the capacity of OAU/AU, inhibited the achievement of desired consensus, and forestalled Africa's desire to achieve a common market.

The advent of the Single European Market (SEM) in 1986, the evolution of the European Union in 1992, and the intensification of regionalist interests in North American Free Trade Area (NAFTA), Organisation of American States (OAS), Asia-Pacific Economic Community (APEC), Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN) that dominated global trade deeply impacted African regionalism (Fawcett 1995: 9). Africa responded by transforming the OAU to the African Union (AU) in 2002 and adopted the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD). The decline of the myth of "Third World collective solidarity" symbolised by the G-77, the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), the South-South Co-operation or OPEC apparently created the space for the promotion of "inner globalism" reflected in regional and sub-regional co-operative ventures. The Third World's loss of its homogeneity from mid-1990s and its extensive and budding diversity of wealth and power, which reduced its relevance as an analytical category, attributed to the collapse of the Second World and the transition of its members to the First World, paved the way for a shift from broad coalitions to regional groupings (Gilpin 1987: 304; Fawcett 1995: 26-7).

The rise of nationalism in Africa was the outcome of European creation of the colonial state, which preceded the existence of any sense of nationhood. Historically, nation and region are linked to each other as actor and stage. Nationalism and regionalism are two competing principles of order very difficult to reconcile since international reconstruction acknowledged "the sovereignty of states and the right of all peoples to self-determination" (Mayall 1995: 186-7). The OAU Charter combined territorial nationalism and regional identity since its membership was more geographical than ideological. Territorial identities competed strongly with racial, linguistic, and religious loyalties and profoundly affected the viability of OAU, which Charter ratified the inviolability of colonially-inherited territorial frontiers even as "ethnic tensions and separatist movements intensified in the post-Cold War era" (Schraeder 2004: 254-5). The rise of nationalism in Africa did not weaken the regional sentiment, but the regional framework could not evolve any viable techniques to contain its disastrous impact. Africa relied on the United Nations for the resolution of conflicts associated with struggles for self-determination as in the cases of Eritrea in 1993 and South Sudan in 2011.

The coming of BRICS, a coalition of Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa between 2006 and 2010 also has critical implications for African regionalism, especially with the membership of South Africa, a significant hegemon in the African system. In 2013, at Durban, South Africa (the birthplace of the African Union), members of BRICS pledged to create a global financial institution and a New Development Bank to which China committed \$41 billion, Brazil, India and Russia \$18 billion each, and South Africa \$5 billion. By 2018, BRICS had a combined nominal GDP of US\$18.6 trillion, about 23.2% of the gross world product, combined GDP of around US\$40.55 trillion (32% of world's GDP) and an estimated US\$4.46 trillion in combined foreign reserves. The members of BRICS have the capacity, individually or collectively, to deepen the "new scramble for Africa" to jeopardise its regionalism, especially with the shift of commitment by South Africa from African regionalism to BRICS.

More so, the state-centric nature of African regional integration processes rejected the "long-standing border trading, much counter-trading and long-distance intra-African trade with their attending production structures", which are very strategic to contemporary African regionalism (Tipoteh 1995: 198-99). The crisis of the African nation-state and reluctance of African leaders to transfer part of their sovereignties, build compromises, or demonstrate commitment to the critical dynamics of regional integration foreclosed African access to vast global trade and economic opportunities (Rasheed 1993: 46; Okigbo 1993: 38). This situation complicated the problem of adoption of an appropriate approach to African regionalism.

Approaches to African Integration

Notwithstanding the bleak picture, Africa cannot afford to continue to remain at the "fringes of development" (Oyebode 2001: 53). However, Africa must not go the European-type integration but pool capacities (Fawcett 1995: 25). It must evolve a radical political economy as the erection and fortification of trading blocs and barriers are being intensified globally (Shaw 1993: 81). Africa needs to transcend orthodox approaches which make Europe "a living laboratory for the integration theory" (Asante 1986: 10; Mayall 1995: 184), and adopt strategies capable of addressing its peculiar conditions (Bourenane 1997: 50). Hence, a critical review of conventional theoretical approaches to regional integration to understand their inherent limitations to the African condition and identify areas of convergence and/or divergence between pan-Africanism and these approaches.

The Federalist Approach

The federalists emphasise political integration and the immediate creation of a supranational or central political authority, transfer of sovereignty, a territorial dispersion of power, a binding commitment to an irrevocable union, a detailed power arrangements, and the final idea of the political system (Smith 1979: 240; Onwuka 1982: 12; Christiansen 2005: 580). However, the collapse of European colonialism left the African region divided into miniscule and vulnerable states engrossed in the search for self-identity. Emergent

African leaders refused to divest some of their powers or transfer their newly acquired sovereignty to a supranational authority, not even among horizontal states (Gruhn 1979: 3). Nkrumah, the leading African federalist, preferred a continental African single currency and common market to sub-regional groupings like the East African Community effort (Mayall 1995: 181). The pre-1963 conferences to ease inter-African states relations rather combined with intense diplomacy and protocol arrangements to heightened inter-states rivalries and nationalism against a federated Africa.

Consequently, the radical Casablanca's pan-Africanist ideals of political integration that represented the federalist approach were substituted with moderate Monrovia's loose regional co-operation and economic integration without the transfer of sovereignty. Afro-enthusiasts, like their European counterparts, canvassed the possibility of transcending the state and nation with the creation of a wider federation and a regional political identity. "Yet, the federalists' efforts were repeatedly frustrated by the continuing vitality of the national idea" (Mayall 1995: 171). This was the highpoint of the cleavage between the federalists represented by the Casablanca bloc and the Brazzaville (later Monrovia) bloc's propositions regarding the course of pan-Africanism for political unity and economic decolonisation.

The Functionalist Approach

This approach sees regional integration as proceeding from the harmonisation of particular governmental structures or economic policies: a process not overtly political, but a steady and continuous aggregation of factors of cooperative mechanism, which can take place in a number of economic and social sectors leaving the political structure of the nation-state largely unaffected (Smith 1979: 241). The functionalists' contention that welfare and security is the *raison d'être* of any political community warrants the conclusion that the provision of society's welfare needs guarantees peace and stability (Onwuka 1982: 12). To functionalism, political integration characterised by the evolution of a supranational authority would be attained after the achievement of economic integration (Smith 1979: 241; Adetula 1996: 14).

The guiding principle of this approach is the notion of gradualism, which combines with the doctrine of ramification and principle of spill-over to contend that regional integration would incrementally lead to a total continental unification (Adetula 1996: 14). The pan-Africanism of the moderate Monrovia bloc clearly converged with this conventional theoretical approach.

Post-independence African leaders' lack of vision that national and regional structures could proceed simultaneously prompted the prioritisation of national political commitment, aggravated the crisis of development, reduced interest in regional integration, and eliminated the possibilities of creating new regional institutions for the development of collective potentials (Gruhn 1979: 6). The functionalists' separation of power and welfare questions the reality that welfarism falls within the confines of political decisions that proceed from power consideration. However, within the context of pan-Africanism, the functionalists became divided over the desirability of regionalism superseding the nation-state with the continental union. Pan-Africanism appeared as an ideology operated at both the regional and state levels, but claimed a regional political identity that did not require the surrender of the sovereignty of national governments. Thus, the persistent reassertion of the primacy of the state in the event of any conflict between the national interest and a regional obligation. Pan-Africanism's lack of gradual integration movement diverged from this theoretical approach

The Neo-functionalist Approach

Hurrell (1995: 59) observes that neo-functionalism played a central role in theorising about European integration. The approach compares an actor in a regional setting to a modern pluralist nation-state motivated by self-interest and re-enacts the nexus between economic and political dynamics in a regional union (Adetula 1996: 15). It espouses the existence of a supranational institution as a necessary apparatus for effective problem-solving since it will undermine the domineering posture of the nation-state (Hurrell 1995: 59; Aspinwall 1995: 478). The neo-functionalist's notion of incrementalism demonstrates that regional

integration should proceed through a collective decision-making process where new decisions emerge piecemeal from inadequately made ones. Neo-functionalists believe regionalism could be enhanced by pluralism "and the particular role played by elites in redefining interests on a broader than national basis" (Hurrell 1995: 66-7). OAU/AU or sub-regional blocs in Africa could not act within the context of the notion of incrementalism (Gruhn 1979: 18). The application of the neo-functional model to Africa is problematic: since actors' expectations are prematurely politicised, piecemeal decisions can easily be manipulated or deadlocked; there is not in existence a positive pluralist socio-political structure in Africa; the struggle over gains of economic regionalism due to limited resources and uneven development is high and will affect the cohesiveness of regional frameworks; lastly, African states lack internal cohesion, while the leaders are reluctant to transfer sovereignty. Hence, the divergence between pan-Africanism and this theoretical approach.

The Customs Union Theory

The customs union approach rests on the concept of international trade guided by David Ricardo's comparative cost advantage and trade liberalisation (Olarenwaju and Falola 1987: 55; Bourenane 1997: 50). It emphasises the creation of a customs union through the harmonisation of economic policies, elimination or reduction of tariff and non-tariff barriers to promote intra-regional trade, and the creation of economies of scale for the allocation and reallocation of resources. It advocates the complementarities of integrating economies, and aims at improving the structure of production and trade and evolving a new trade mechanism based on regional specialisation. A custom union envision a larger than purely national markets and intra-regional policy coordination and harmonisation in a variety of strategic areas (Robson 1990: 130). Asante (1986: 11) explains that the creation of a customs union usually involves long time periods for fruition so that the initial impact is an expectation regarding future market opportunities rather than existing trade patterns.

However, African economies are predominantly competitive and traditional, producing primary

agricultural commodities and natural resources, and competing for the same external markets (Asante 1986: 10; Olarenwaju and Falola 1987: 56; Adetula 1996: 23; Bourenane 1997: 52). Since African economies are predominantly competitive and not complementary (Mayall 1995: 182-83), pan-African regionalism through customs union approach may deepen economic inefficiency as most competitive producers of the same products would aggregate and become excluded from the market following Jacob Viner's trade creation and diversion thesis (Bourenane 1997: 52). More so, the removal of tariff barriers among African economies may not have any redistributive effects on the regional pattern of production like replacing high cost of production at home with lower cost of supplies from union members (Hazzlewood 1967: 6). Since this approach pays attention to the allocation and reallocation of resources and shifting patterns of trade on the basis of comparative cost advantage, it is limited in the evaluation of the need for and effects of integration in Africa (Robson 1968: 33); regional bodies in Africa driven by common market desires like the East African Community (EAC) died sudden death without meeting the expectations due to competition for external markets and intra-regional rivalry (Green 1990: 108). Hence, the divergence between pan-Africanism and this conventional approach.

The Marxist Approach

Marxism sees European integration as a western capitalist ploy to generate profits via the internationalisation of finance capital. The Single European Market (SEM) reflected the concentration of capital and internalisation of firms rather than the desire of welfare-maximising governments to rationalise the allocation of resources among members. European market integration is the consequence, not the precursor, of the transformation of production and trade favouring larger firms, while excluding and improvising small-scale enterprises through market displacements (Bourenane 1997: 52). To Marxism, European integration was not intended to reduce the nation-state, but to shelter and protect "particular domestic project" crafted around Keynesianism, social welfare, and corporatist social arrangements

(Hurrell 1995: 70). Marxism blames the failure of African integration efforts on the interference of western capitalist states, and the domineering interests of African elites doing the bidding of foreign capital at the expense of national development and self-reliance.

A point of convergence: Afro-Marxists espouse Nkrumah's radicalism to produce genuine political independence and complete delinking from capitalist neo-colonial forces. Following this approach, therefore, Africa should not rely on free market forces, but pursue pan-African regionalist efforts towards the rational use of available resources through a planned and centralised approach. Like the new African regionalism supported by the ECA, Marxism advocates sub-regional integration for economic development and eventual unification (Gruhn 1979: 16). The point of divergence is that although apparently appealing, the application of this model to the African integration process smacks of a failure in view of the crash of the Soviet Union and the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance (COMECON) (Bourenane 1997: 53), and the impossibility of compromise building in Africa for attainment of a central authority.

The Dependency Theory

The *dependency* approach reconceptualises the purpose of regional integration in Africa to aim at creating economic stimulus for development through regional integration to counteract the conditioning impact of external influences in the underdeveloped world. It warns against over-capitalisation and criticises the role of industrial bourgeoisie (Onwuka 1991: 5). It gives priority to the restructuring of the exploitative unequal trade relations between African and the developed western economies, and the possibility of overcoming dependence. As a convergence, the LPA strategy for African economic decolonisation and collective self-reliance originated from the *dependencia* standpoint. However, reducing the dilemma of pan-African regionalism simply to the effects of European capitalist needs is only seeking reforms rather than restructuring domestic political economy.

The Development Economics School of Thought

This approach views European regional economic integration as the historical product of evolving technical, economic and social structures or the product of conscious efforts of human societies acting collectively to improve their economic conditions, and regional integration resulting from social transformation, which cannot just occur under any conditions. It strongly argues that effective regional integration could only be achieved through an industrialisation-driven process sustainable by social forces capable of organising and supporting it (Bourenane 1997: 53). This approach assigns a secondary role to the social dimension of the integration process making its adoption in the African integration process very problematic since its economies are industrially underdeveloped and backward, and unable to equip the states to tackle the globalisation onslaught, thereby raised a strong point divergence between it and pan-Africanism.

The Transactionalist Theory

Transactionalism, developed by Karl Deustch, argues for the reduction of conflicts and the development of regional community through increased and accelerated transactions among private and public persons of different societies. It sees integration as a social process towards a security community-building through viable social communication (Howe 1995: 42-4). It backs the retention of pre-colonial historical transactions, cultural interactions and commercial exchanges to accelerate community-building and regional integration (Gruhn 1979: 15; Hurrell 1995: 65-6). Regarding pan-Africanism, *transactionalism* espouses the retention of colonially-inherited links of language and boundaries and the simultaneous development of viable post-independence ones. However, given the tragically divergent colonial heritage, and the sanctity of the state territoriality, and the division of ethnic groups like Ewe between Ghana and Togo, Hausa between Nigeria and Niger, and Yoruba between Benin and Nigeria, the achievement of regional integration is difficult (Asiwaju 2004: 211). Perhaps, post-colonial African leaders' defence of inherited boundaries as sacrosanct profoundly blocks the transfer of sovereignty, pooling of resources and harmonisation

of economic policies (Mayall 1995: 176; Bonchuk 2012: 233).

From OAU to AU/NEPAD

The pan-Africanist efforts of the colonial period established the OAU in the independence decade, while the new regionalism prompted its transition to the AU (Asuk 2003: 109-119). The move towards the transition began several decades before the Muammar Al-Gaddafi-hosted Sirte Conference of 1999, which proposed the replacement of the OAU by the AU to eliminate boundaries (Adetula 2005: 170-2). In 1960, twelve independent Francophone states advocated a close relationship with the EEC to originate a neo-colonial bonding (Amate 1986: 44). They created the Brazzaville group committed to the Union of African and Malagasy States (UAMS) against the Ghana-Guinea-Mali Union of African States' (UAS) vision of a "United States of Africa ..." By January 1961, Nkrumah had abandoned this union and embraced the Casablanca group that advocated the complete liquidation of neo-colonialism in Africa (Amate 1986: 46-7). These divergent groups formed links with the East/West blocs to deepen the vulnerability of African economies. Taubman's unsuccessful attempt in May 1961 to broker a *modus vivendi* led to Liberia's membership of the conservative Monrovia group to advocate for a gradual pooling of resources for economic efficiency (Amate 1986: 49).

The January 1962 Lagos conference for merger and the boycott of the Casablanças warranted the adoption of the Monrovia's draft charter of an inter-African and Malagasy States Organisation. Ethiopia's Emperor Haile Selassie's effort to resolve the antagonism waited for Algeria's independence on 1 November 1962, a major issue in the Casablanca's agenda. At the Addis Ababa Conference of May 1963, when the OAU was established, Morocco was absent because Mauritania was recognised and invited to the summit, while Togo boycotted due to the non-recognition of its military regime by Nigeria and Liberia (Amate 1986: 49-51). The formation of OAU was regarded as the institutionalisation of pan-Africanism (the creation of a critical pan-African institution) though the contestation between the

conservatives' functionalist and radicals' federalist approaches produced a very weak compromise in the OAU Charter (Adetula 2005: 158).

Subsequently, the OAU assumed the status of an ultra-state political community of members with common identity and interest (Mayall 1995: 177). However, progress towards regional economic integration has been thwarted by the dominant outward links of the African economies, the legacy of colonial ideologies, the strong sense of affiliation to different monetary zones, reluctance to relinquish national sovereignty, and the similarities of weak economic structures (Rasheed 1993: 46). Between 1980 and 1994, the OAU having achieved its political decolonisation and liberation objectives redirected its attention to regional economic integration adopted the Monrovia Strategy for Economic Development of Africa (1979), the Lagos Plan of Action (1980), and the African Economic Community (1994). The non-implementation of the LPA strategy and failure to achieve economies of scale for the allocation and reallocation of resources in Africa prompted the creation of the African Economic Community (AEC) by the Abuja Treaty of June 3, 1991 (ARIA II 2006: 35). The transition from the OAU to the African Union, which began in 1999 ended on July 9, 2002 at Durban, South Africa.

The transition was applauded as part of Africa's constant engagement and dialogue for a redefinition of strategies and tactics of social transformation to enhance its relevance within the global *realpolitik* (Oyebode 2001: 53). Pan-Africanism as expressed in the OAU was a very weak and emotionally thin form of identification. However, the AU was modelled on the EU thereby repeating the same old mistake of adopting foreign model of development (ARIA II 2006: 18), and pursuing political unity and economic integration simultaneously (Adetula 2005: 160-61). The transition and the adoption of NEPAD in line with the neo-liberal ideology complicated the irrational mimicking of the western models and stagnated Africa's regional integration efforts for economic efficiency. The strategic orientation of NEPAD is still state-centric without the inputs of African peoples making it incapable of resolving the *Afrosclerosis* (Asuk 2011: 133-47). The AU Constitutive Act like AEC Treaty of 1991

emphasised "the co-ordination, harmonization, and progressive integration of the activities of regional economic communities of which they are members with the activities of the Community" (ARIA II 2006: 1).

Conclusion

Colonial trajectories and divergences created complex dichotomies and rivalries that characterised the post-colonial African system, and impacted critically on the approach to and prospects of African regional integration process. Africa's attempts at regional and sub-regional frameworks that imitated the European model always had little impact because they are too ambitious in view of the conditions and resources of member-states. Regional and sub-regional economic integration processes in Africa are strictly state-centric and devoid of inputs from the social masses. The evolution of many weak and unviable states makes the process of regional community-building almost impossible in Africa. Regionalism should not serve as an alternative to nationalism, but as a supplement to it. The work concludes that contemporary pan-Africanist initiative embodied in the AU/NEPAD did not incorporate an African-oriented development approach characterised by a bottom-up people-driven regional integration strategy. African regional economic integration should not, therefore, be approached from a single level model due to the complexity of the African condition, but the synthesis of useful variables from the various models into an appropriate people-oriented strategy. Therefore, the pragmatism of the pan-Africanist ideology developed in the LPA/FAL towards economic decolonisation woven around collective self-reliance should be revived and pursued vigorously.

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